

PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract: Teaching English online with the use of various kinds of Internet technologies is currently a very relevant topic. The online format gives students new opportunities in the process of learning the English language, and also helps to learn to solve emerging problems on their own and to be personally responsible for the learning process. However, it should be noted that the effectiveness of teaching English as a foreign language using such methods depends to a large extent on the student's personal interest in learning it. The issue of integrating the Internet into education, particularly its application in teaching foreign languages, is currently very relevant since many goals and objectives of teaching are realized in the most efficient way. This article is a brief analysis of the advantages and disadvantages of teaching English online, which will be useful for teachers organizing the teaching and learning process in an online format.

Key words: Internet technologies, online format, Internet, distance learning, e-learning, face-to-face learning, advantages, disadvantages, COVID-19 pandemic

Introduction

Internet technologies are being increasingly integrated into many aspects of our lives, including education. In this context, an approach for applying digital tools in foreign language education is required. Today's learners begin the process of mastering digital technologies from early childhood. Communication on social

networks, Internet games, video calls form an integral part of the life of any modern teenager. It is worth noting that this generation of schoolchildren is very sensitive to all changes in the digital environment, and therefore, teachers must also be able to keep up with the times. David Goodrum claims that —digital education is generating new learning opportunities as students engage in online, digital environments and as faculty change educational practices through the use of hybrid courses, personalized instruction, new collaboration models and a wide array of innovative, engaging learning strategies. [10] This means that the issue of using new technologies that will make it possible to create interesting and, most importantly, useful lessons, is more relevant today than ever.

Online teaching is actively used in almost all educational institutions. The rapid transition to this format was facilitated by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020, but it is notable that the issue of using distance learning technologies in education has been considered before. This is evidenced by various articles of scientific and practical conferences. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, most of the research was focused on universities, whereas teachers and learners in primary and secondary schools lacked experience with emergency remote instruction.

How to learn a foreign language faster and easier: online or in-person? Does one need face-to-face classes? Definitely, these questions cannot be answered unequivocally, since this method of teaching a foreign language has its advantages and disadvantages. In this article, we will consider a number of the so-called "pluses" and "minuses" of teaching a foreign language in online format.

The characteristics of distance learning

To date, much attention is paid to the problem of distance learning in pedagogical literature. Analysis of local and foreign theory and practice of distance education made it possible to note the characteristic features inherent in distance education. Among them are the following:

- Flexibility - students study at a convenient time for themselves, in a

convenient place and at a convenient pace. Everyone can study as much as he/she personally needs to master and obtain necessary knowledge in the chosen subject. The Internet encourages learners to study autonomously and speeds up the delivery of high-quality learning materials within the scope of a single lesson.

- Modularity - the basis of distance learning programs is a modular principle. Each individual subject (training course) is directly related to the content of a specific subject area. This allows a curriculum to be tailored to individual or group needs from a set of independent training courses.

- Functionality – it is about new functions of the teacher and his/her new role as a mentor with much more responsibilities. Being able to teach a lesson online is a skill that can only be learned through practice. It is important to understand what teaching approaches will be used in teaching a specific course. In fact, the student taking online course will have certain responsibilities that differ significantly from the traditional ones. [1; 18] The listed features determine the advantages of distance education over other forms of education, but, at the same time, present certain specific requirements to both the teacher and the learner. [2; 37]

The student's independent cognitive activity (learning, not teaching) is at the center of the process of teaching a foreign language. The learners are exposed to independent activities to master various types of speech activity and the formation of necessary skills and abilities. Hence, on the one hand, a more flexible education system is needed, allowing the acquisition of knowledge where and when it is convenient for the learner. Independent acquisition of knowledge should not be passive. On the contrary, the student from the very beginning should be involved in active cognitive activity, not limited to mastering knowledge, but certainly applying it for solving various communicative tasks. [4; 36]

On the other hand, a student must not only have user skills in working with a computer, but also methods of working with authentic information that he/she encounters in various Internet resources. The point is that learners should be good

at working with different types of resources such as reference books and dictionaries that are suggested as a part of the English language course or exist autonomously on various servers. [3; 82-89]

Distance learning, individualized in its essence, should not, at the same time, exclude the possibility of communication not only with the teacher, but also with other learners. Socialization problems are very relevant in distance learning. The system of control over the assimilation of knowledge and methods of cognitive activity, the ability to apply the acquired knowledge of the English language in various problem situations should be systematic, built on the basis of supportive feedback. [5; 10]

The advantages of distance learning

Undoubtedly, the main advantage of this method over others is that modern technologies make it possible for absolutely any student to study a subject at a convenient pace and mode. Moreover, a learner can independently determine how much time he/she will devote to studying this subject, draw up his own schedule of classes with a convenient schedule for him.

Many high school students think that the process of teaching foreign languages in the classroom is boring due to the frequency of doing monotonous exercises using only paper-based resources. Classes in online format, as a rule, are structured differently since various video lessons, active games and educational platforms are included. In addition, there is no need to purchase printed materials as all teaching aids can be copied or downloaded online. In addition to textbooks, it is possible to use additional authentic materials from various sources, which are selected to achieve the personal goals of learners. The teacher motivates one to speak from the very first lesson, gives useful advice and corrects mistakes in the chat. The atmosphere of these activities enables the learner to be liberated and easily step out of the comfort zone.

The homework assignment can be submitted in written format (in other

words, the learner can send the completed exercises by e-mail), as well as complete them on any learning platform that the teacher has access to, or answer orally during an online lesson.

The disadvantages of distance learning

It is obvious that online English language learning has its own set of disadvantages. One of them is dependence on technical means and Internet accessibility. For example, many teachers ask the question: what to do if the webcam does not work or it is not possible to use it? Many people think that a webcam is always used in online lessons, but this is far from the case. Practice shows that during work the teacher may not use a video camera, thus maximizing the student's attention. This is very effective in developing listening skills, usually much faster than during a traditional classroom session where listening is reinforced with other types of communication.

It is worth noting the negative impact of computer technology on human health. If a person already spends a lot of time at the computer and this applies to both students and teachers, then the additional time spent in an online lesson at the screen will have a negative impact on health. Being constantly online is the new reality, but the truth is that using a computer or a tablet all the time can cause poor vision, strain injuries and other physical problems.

It is impossible not to note the problem of socialization of the individual, which affects all those studying remotely. The lack of face-to-face communication between a teacher and students, as a rule, is not very comfortable for both parties from a psychological point of view since online training excludes moments associated with an individual approach and personal education. [6; 35] No matter how hard we tried to fully transfer human communication to online platforms, no matter how natural it seems to form relationships behind computer screens, a virtual environment is just not human. Nothing can replace human contact.

Despite all the preparation and accurate design of e-learning course, there is

no guarantee that the messages will get across. There is always the risk that learners just go through the material without paying any attention.

Conclusion

It needs to be emphasized that completely new requirements are imposed on the personality of the teacher who organizes the process of teaching a foreign language in an online format. As noted earlier, being able to teach a lesson online is a skill that can only be learned through practice. It is important to understand on what conceptual pedagogical provisions it is advisable to build a modern distance learning course in a foreign language. The main task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. The use of the online format does not at all exclude traditional methods, but is harmoniously combined with them at all stages of training: introduction, practice, application, testing. This allows not only to increase the effectiveness of learning, but also to stimulate high school students to study English independently. There may also be game components that facilitate understanding and assimilation of the presented material. Success to a large extent depends on how accurate the material is organized, where part of the lessons can be implemented using multimedia courses, and ongoing assessment can be carried out using the testing system. [7; 38]

It should be noted, however, that the effectiveness of language programs is associated with the conditions of the environment in which they are used. In a monolingual society, a foreign language is considered as the content of the course, and not as a medium for communication. Therefore, it is almost impossible to practice the acquired skills outside the classroom. On the other hand, language learning requires student interaction in order to achieve the desired result. Considering these contextual conditions, it should be noted that even when using computer technologies in teaching, the presence of a teacher who facilitates the educational process is necessary. [8; 167] In any case, the situational context must

be taken into account and necessary modifications made that best suit the needs of the students and the tasks set. [9; 292]

To conclude, distance learning is a type of education that allows students to attend classes and complete courses without physically attending a school. The popularity of distance learning has been progressively rising prior to COVID-19. The numbers grew rapidly during the pandemic as a result of global school closures and the demand for remote education. Many educational institutions were forced to design online education programs and provide distance learning technology training to both teachers and students. Thus, teaching a foreign language in an online format undoubtedly has its own advantages and disadvantages that should be taken into account when organizing educational activities. But in any case, it should be noted that distance learning is an integral part of our future.

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